

Bouveret Syndrome as a Cause of High Intestinal Obstruction in an Older Adult: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Bouveret syndrome is a rare cause of gastric outlet obstruction secondary to the impaction of a gallstone in the duodenum or stomach through a bilioenteric fistula. It accounts for 1–3% of biliary ileus cases and occurs primarily in elderly women with multiple comorbidities. This report describes an exceptional case of Bouveret syndrome complicated by grade III cholangitis and septic shock in a nonagenarian patient, highlighting the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in frail older adults. **Case report:** A 91-year-old woman with a history of geriatric frailty was admitted with progressive intolerance to oral intake, nausea, food-containing vomiting, abdominal pain, jaundice, and fever. Laboratory studies showed leukocytosis, anemia, acute kidney injury, hyperbilirubinemia, and elevated liver enzymes. Abdominal computed tomography revealed gastric distension, pneumobilia, and an abrupt narrowing of the duodenal lumen, consistent with mechanical obstruction. Emergency exploratory laparotomy identified multiple gallstones impacted in the duodenum and a cholecystoduodenal fistula. Partial gastrectomy with stone extraction and fistula repair was performed. Histopathological analysis confirmed acute and chronic inflammatory changes associated with the fistula. Despite appropriate surgical management, the patient developed refractory septic shock and died on the second day of intensive care due to multiorgan failure. **Conclusion:** Bouveret syndrome should be considered in elderly patients presenting with gastric outlet obstruction and signs of cholangitis. This case demonstrates that, even with timely surgical intervention, the prognosis for nonagenarian patients with frailty and sepsis remains poor. The main lesson is the need for a multidisciplinary and individualized approach that carefully evaluates surgical risk, expected benefits, and the patient’s quality of life.

KEYWORDS: Bouveret syndrome; biliary ileus; gastric outlet obstruction; gallstone disease; cholecystoenteric fistula; cholangitis; geriatric frailty.

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INTRODUCTION

Bouveret syndrome is defined as gastric outlet obstruction secondary to a gallstone impacted in the duodenum or stomach. It is an uncommon cause of gastric outlet obstruction originating from gallstones and accounts for 1–3% of biliary ileus cases, which in turn complicates 0.3–4%

of cholelithiasis cases. It occurs more frequently in older adults and in women, with a reported median age of 74 years and a female-to-male ratio of approximately 2:1.^{1,2}

Its pathophysiology is related to the formation of bilioenteric fistulas, which occur in 0.3–5% of patients with gallstone disease. These fistulas develop when the walls of the biliary

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system and the intestine become chronically inflamed and adherent; increased intraluminal pressure due to obstruction leads to ischemia and local necrosis, allowing the gallstone to perforate the walls and migrate into the gastrointestinal tract. Fistulas may be cholecystogastric, which are less common, or cholecystoduodenal, which are the most frequent.

Once gallstones enter the gastrointestinal tract, their impaction and the site of obstruction depend on their size and location. Stones smaller than 2.5 cm usually pass through the small intestine without difficulty, although they may cause biliary ileus; this condition is more common with larger stones. Most gallstones become impacted in the terminal ileum, whereas duodenal obstruction is less common. When obstruction occurs at this level, Bouveret syndrome develops. This syndrome has a high mortality rate—up to 12%—mainly due to advanced age and frailty of affected patients. In rare cases, fistula formation and stone migration may be caused by malignant processes.^{2,10}

Diagnosis of Bouveret syndrome requires a combination of clinical and imaging findings. Plain radiography has low sensitivity and rarely demonstrates the complete Rigler triad. Ultrasound may suggest the diagnosis by showing pneumobilia or gastric dilation, although its limitations are notable in the presence of bowel gas. Currently, computed tomography is the most widely used diagnostic method and can identify fistulas, inflammatory changes, and stone characteristics; however, up to one-quarter of stones may not be visualized due to isoattenuation, making MRCP useful in selected cases. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy confirms the diagnosis in most patients and allows initial therapeutic attempts, although the success rate of endoscopic extraction is limited, and in many cases the definitive diagnosis is made intraoperatively.^{2,3}

We present the case of a 91-year-old patient with Bouveret syndrome complicated by grade III cholangitis and septic shock, with the aim of highlighting diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in frail older adults and comparing this outcome with those reported in the literature.

CASE REPORT

The patient was a 91-year-old mestizo woman from Telchac, Yucatán, previously employed as a seamstress, currently unemployed, and dependent on her family for activities of daily living. She weighed 50 kg and measured 1.48 m in height, presenting clinical signs of frailty. She had no known chronic degenerative diseases or recent abdominal surgeries and denied transfusions, medication allergies, smoking, or regular alcohol consumption. She reported no relevant family history or known genetic predisposition. Her diet was typical of the region, rich in carbohydrates and fats, with low protein and vegetable intake.

Approximately one and a half weeks prior to admission, she developed progressive intolerance to oral intake, nausea, and food-containing vomiting, followed by diffuse colicky abdominal pain of moderate to severe intensity radiating to

the right lumbar region, unquantified fever, dark urine, and pale stools. Subsequently, she experienced deterioration in general condition, including asthenia, adynamia, diaphoresis, and obtundation. She was evaluated at a secondary-level hospital, where normocytic normochromic anemia with hemoglobin of 7.5 g/dL was documented, prompting referral to a tertiary-care hospital.

At admission, she was conscious with a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 14, appeared distressed, and had generalized jaundice. Vital signs were as follows: heart rate 86 bpm, blood pressure 110/60 mmHg, temperature 36.2 °C, mean arterial pressure 76.6 mmHg, and oxygen saturation 95% with supplemental oxygen. Physical examination revealed a soft abdomen, tender to palpation with localized peritoneal signs, preserved bowel sounds, and no palpable organomegaly. Extremities were symmetrical with no edema and delayed capillary refill of three seconds.

Laboratory studies showed leukocytosis of 20,090/ μ L, anemia with hemoglobin 7.5 g/dL, platelets initially at 275,000/ μ L decreasing to 58,000/ μ L, elevated creatinine up to 5.3 mg/dL, urea 241 mg/dL, total bilirubin 16.7 mg/dL with direct fraction 7.5 mg/dL, elevated liver enzymes (AST 144 U/L, ALT 63 U/L, ALP 340 U/L, GGT 158 U/L), hypoalbuminemia of 3.0 g/dL, and mild coagulopathy with INR 1.35.

Abdominal ultrasound showed hepatomegaly with preserved echogenicity, dilation of the intrahepatic bile ducts up to 9 mm, absence of the gallbladder in its anatomical location, and a cystic image with a fluid–fluid level. Abdominopelvic CT revealed marked gastric distension with heterogeneous contents, abrupt narrowing at the duodenal junction, and a gastric volume of approximately 3.5L, with displacement of the liver, spleen, and pancreas (Figure 1). These findings were initially interpreted as duodenal intestinal torsion with gastric volvulus; however, intraoperative confirmation established the diagnosis of Bouveret syndrome.

Based on clinical, laboratory, and imaging findings, diagnoses included abdominal sepsis with a SOFA score of 8, grade III acute cholangitis according to the Tokyo Guidelines, septic shock, moderate anemia, acute kidney injury (AKI III), urinary tract infection without isolated pathogen, and high intestinal obstruction secondary to Bouveret syndrome. Management in the critical care unit was initiated with intravenous fluids, oxygen therapy, broad-spectrum antibiotics (ceftriaxone 2 g IV every 24 h and metronidazole 500 mg IV every 8 h), transfusion of two packed red blood cells and one unit of fresh frozen plasma, vasopressor support, gastric and thromboembolic prophylaxis, and strict hemodynamic monitoring.

Due to persistent signs of acute abdomen, emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed. Multiple gallstones impacted in the duodenum at the pyloric level were identified, causing intestinal obstruction, along with a cholecystoduodenal fistula and dilation of intra- and extrahepatic bile ducts (Figures 2 and 3). A partial

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gastrectomy with exploration and extraction of multiple stones, fistula repair, biliary diversion, and placement of drains was carried out. Estimated blood loss was 200 mL, and no immediate complications occurred. Histopathology reported fibroconnective and adipose tissue with generalized edema, focal vascular congestion, and nonspecific acute and chronic inflammation, findings consistent with inflammatory changes associated with the fistula, although insufficient to fully characterize the lesion, in agreement with the intraoperative finding of a cholecystoduodenal fistula.

In the immediate postoperative period, the patient was admitted to the intensive care unit under invasive mechanical ventilation and vasopressor support. She developed acute kidney injury and persistent septic shock, with rapid progression to multiorgan failure. Despite advanced supportive measures, the patient died on the second day of ICU hospitalization due to refractory septic shock in the context of Bouveret syndrome complicated by acute cholangitis and geriatric frailty.

Figure 1. Abdominal computed tomography scan showing hyperdense gallstones within the duodenal lumen, pneumobilia, and gastric distension.

Figures 2 and 3. Multiple gallstones impacted within the duodenal lumen, observed during surgical exploration.

DISCUSSION

Bouveret syndrome is a rare and challenging clinical entity that combines diagnostic complexity with a high risk of

morbidity and mortality, particularly in older adults with multiple comorbidities. Its low incidence limits the availability of standardized protocols; therefore, case reports

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are essential sources of clinical learning, helping to better understand variability in presentation, therapeutic strategies, and outcomes.^{2,8,9}

Patchipala et al. (2025) described a case of Bouveret syndrome in a 73-year-old man treated surgically, initially via laparoscopy and subsequently converted to open surgery, with favorable recovery after gallstone extraction. In contrast, our nonagenarian patient—frail and septic—had a fatal outcome despite surgical resolution. This comparison highlights how advanced age and a complex clinical context significantly worsen prognosis, underscoring the need to individualize management in elderly patients with this syndrome.⁴

Similarly, Alshaikh et al. reported a case of Bouveret syndrome managed with single-stage surgery involving stone extraction and fistula repair, with favorable postoperative evolution. They note that although endoscopic methods are often considered first-line, their low success rate makes surgery the definitive treatment, particularly in younger patients with fewer comorbidities. In contrast, in our nonagenarian patient with frailty and grade III cholangitis, surgical resolution did not prevent a fatal outcome, emphasizing that advanced age and septic status critically influence prognosis and require individualized decision-making.⁵

Louis et al. (2025) presented a case of a 31-year-old woman with complicated Bouveret syndrome initially associated with a hepatic abscess and acute cholecystitis. After drainage and antibiotics, symptoms recurred three years later, and duodenal obstruction due to a cholecystoduodenal fistula was confirmed. She underwent open cholecystectomy with duodenal repair and had a favorable recovery. This case demonstrates that even younger patients may experience a complex clinical course requiring definitive surgical management. In comparison, our frail nonagenarian patient developed rapid deterioration and died despite intervention. The contrast between both cases highlights that age, baseline health status, and presence of sepsis are key prognostic determinants, and treatment must be tailored to the clinical context.⁶

Chatterjee and De (2024) described a 70-year-old man with Bouveret syndrome diagnosed through endoscopy and imaging showing an impacted stone distal to the pylorus and a cholecystoenteric fistula. Endoscopic extraction failed, and the patient required laparotomy with gastrotomy and stone extraction without fistula resection. Postoperative recovery was favorable. This report contrasts with our patient, who—beyond obstruction—presented grade III cholangitis and sepsis, progressing to multiorgan failure and death despite surgical intervention. This comparison further illustrates how advanced age, frailty, and septic status significantly affect outcomes, even when the obstruction is surgically resolved.⁷

A major strength of our case was the early identification of the obstruction and immediate surgical management, which allowed technical resolution of the obstructive event.

However, limitations stem from the patient's baseline condition: advanced age, frailty, and severe sepsis reduced therapeutic options and contributed to the unfavorable outcome. Furthermore, the patient's critical condition at admission precluded less invasive alternatives such as endoscopic extraction, which has been attempted as first-line therapy in other series.

The literature consistently reports that mortality in Bouveret syndrome reaches up to 12% and increases significantly in elderly patients with frailty and comorbidities. While younger patients in the reviewed reports achieved favorable recovery after surgical resolution, our patient's severe sepsis and multiorgan failure contributed to a fatal outcome. Additionally, Bouveret syndrome represents 1–3% of biliary ileus cases and less than 0.5% of all gallstone-related complications. Mortality may reach 30% in frail older adults, reinforcing the importance of early diagnosis and individualized management.

In our case, computed tomography was fundamental to confirming obstruction and fistula formation, consistent with literature identifying CT as the most sensitive modality for this diagnosis. Although endoscopic techniques are a less invasive alternative, their success rate is low in cases involving large stones, and availability may be limited—further supporting surgery as the definitive treatment.

Our case demonstrates that while surgical intervention resolved the obstruction, frailty, advanced age, and septic status explain the fatal outcome. These characteristics reflect that prognosis in such patients depends more on baseline clinical factors and systemic context than on the surgical technique itself.

The primary lesson from this case is that in Bouveret syndrome affecting nonagenarian patients, surgery may not alter mortality despite resolving the obstruction; frailty must be considered a key determinant in clinical decision-making. This report contributes to the evidence on Bouveret syndrome in elderly patients, emphasizing the need for individualized management protocols that include comprehensive geriatric assessment and multidisciplinary care.

Finally, due to the patient's death, her perspective could not be directly obtained; however, her family received continuous updates regarding the severity and poor prognosis and provided informed consent for publication for academic purposes.

CONCLUSION

Bouveret syndrome is an uncommon cause of gastric outlet obstruction secondary to the passage of a gallstone through a bilioenteric fistula. Diagnosis is often delayed due to nonspecific presentation, particularly in geriatric patients with multiple comorbidities. In this case, the nonagenarian patient presented with advanced disease, duodenal impaction of gallstones, and an unfavorable outcome despite timely surgical management. This underscores the high morbidity and mortality associated with this condition in frail older

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adults and highlights the need for individualized multidisciplinary evaluation that balances therapeutic benefit against surgical risk.

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Ethical considerations: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, procedures performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic interventions and for publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and institutional guidelines.

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